

SUSPENSE AND FORESHADOWING AS GENRE

*O'zbekiston respublikas Ichki ishlar vazirligi Buxoro
akademik litseyi ingliz tili fani o'qituvchilari:*

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Annotation: In this article, I try to explain suspense and its function in literary works. With the help of this thought-provoking, One can widen his knowledge about suspense.

Key words: suspense, danger, foreshadowing, annoying, hope.

Suspense is a feeling of uncertainty and anxiety about the outcome of certain actions, most often referring to an audience's perceptions in a dramatic work. Suspense is not exclusive to fiction, though. Suspense may operate in any situation where there is a lead up to a big event or dramatic moment, with tension being a primary emotion felt as part of the situation. In the kind of suspense described by film directed **Alfred Hitchcock**, an audience experiences suspense when they expect something bad to happen and have a superior perspective on events in the drama's hierarchy of knowledge, yet they are powerless to intervene to prevent it from happening. In broader definitions of suspense, this emotion arises when someone is aware of his lack of knowledge about the development of a meaningful event: thus, suspense is a combination of anticipation and uncertainly dealing with the obscurity of the future. In terms of **narrative expectations**, it may be contrasted with mystery or curiosity and surprise.

Suspense comes in many different sizes, big and small. According to Greek philosopher Aristotle in his book „Poetics”, suspense is an important building

block of literature. An very broad terms, it consists of having some real danger looming and a ray of hope .

The two common outcomes are the danger hitting, whereby the audience will feel sorrowful . The hopes being realized , whereby the audience will first feel joy, then satisfaction . If there is no hope , the audience will feel despair. Something other than the danger happening is a deus ex machina.

Some authors have tried to explain the „ paradox of suspense” , namely; a narrative tension that remains effective even when uncertainty is naturalized , because repeat audiences know exactly how the story resolves. Some theories assume that true repeat audiences are extremely rare because, in reiteration ,we usually forget many details of the story and the interest arises due to these holes of memory; others claim that uncertainly remains even for often told stories because, during the immersion in the fictional world, we forget fictionally what we know factually or because we expect fictional worlds to look like real world , where exact repetition of an event is impossible.

The position of Yanal is more radical and postulates that narrative tension that remains effective in true repetition should be clearly distinguished from genuine suspense ,because uncertainly is part of the definition of suspense . Baroni proposes to name „ rappel “ this kind of suspense whose excitement relies on the ability of the audience to anticipate perfectly what is to come, a precognition that is particularly enjoyable for children dealing with well-known fairy tales . Baroni adds that another kind of suspense without uncertainty can emerge with the occasional contradiction between what the reader knows about the future and what he desire, especially in tragedy, when the protagonist eventually dies or fails.

Foreshadowing and Suspense

Suspense is an important element of any story . So you're not writing romantic suspense ? That doesn't have to involve car chases and psychopath stalking your heroine. There is suspense in everything from tense boardroom meeting to a Regency ball where the heroine risks being compromised by a cad to a frontier

heroine facing off alone against a dust storm. Lives don't have to be at a stake . You ,as the author, can generate suspense out of relatively mundane things, as long as they are important to the story , such as whether the stuffy hero will walk under the door just before the pail of water falls down . Foreshadowing is one tool you can use to heighten the suspense . It gets a separate section because it can get pretty complicated, and it can be hard to foreshadow events just right.

Leaving your Readers in suspenders.

Writers have described suspense as being like a roller coaster. The trip up to the top is the suspense, and the fast trip down the hill is the pay-off. I prefer to think of suspense as being like the Thursday of a working week. The week's almost over, you're looking forward to Friday night and the weekend.

Climax Live up to the Suspense

As we know, sometimes, the anticipation is more exciting than the actual event. A nice sunny Thursday can turn into a rainy weekend filled with chores. A suspenseful novel can sputter out when the solution is unfolded. How do you plant the best ending for your story? Start by thinking of the reader. What would be interesting, and shake the reader? Is the resolution too pat? If so, make it harder for your characters. Oh, think of your characters, too, of course. Do they have enough obstacles? Are they reacting in character to what happens. Oh, and make sure the villains get an appropriate comeuppance.

If the suspense is good enough, readers may forgive a relatively weak ending. However, they may be less likely to pick up your next book. The best writers of suspense know that they can get away with teasing the reader for only so long. Eventually , there has to be a pay- off.

Suspense

- The condition of being insecure or uncertain:

The matter of the succession remained in suspense.

- Anxiety or apprehension resulting from an uncertain, undecided , or mysterious situation:

Their father’s illness kept them in a state of suspense.

- Pleasurable excitement and anticipation regarding an outcome, such as the ending of a mystery novel, excitement felt at the approach of the climax:

A play of terrifying suspense.

- The state or quality of being undecided , uncertain .

Used literatures:

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2. The World Book Encyclopedia.